

The Kaniṣka era in Gupta records

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1. Dropped hundreds or the saeculum

In a previous publication (Falk 2001) it was shown that there is a mathematical formula preserved in an astronomical text written by one Sphujiddhvaja in the 4th century which directly links the well-known Śaka era with what the text calls the *koṣāṇa* era. This formula tells us to add 149 to any *koṣāṇa* date to get the corresponding year in the Śaka era. Therefore, it seems virtually impossible to maintain the old idea that the *śaka* and the *kuṣāṇa* era are identical.

Through Sphujiddhvaja's formula, the beginning of the *koṣāṇa* era is fixed to spring AD 227. It was expected that the term *koṣāṇa* would refer to the era used by the Kuṣāṇa dynasty, written *kuṣāṇa* in Brāhmī, *kuṣāṇa*, *guṣāṇa* or *khuṣāṇa* in Kharoṣṭhī. Although Kuṣāṇa texts are dated to a variety of eras, only the one starting with Kaniṣka I seems to be so intimately linked to that family as to deserve to be called *koṣāṇa*.

The starting date of AD 227, as given by Sphujiddhvaja is about 100 years later than the expected beginning of the Kaniṣka era taking into account numismatic material and extra-Indian, particularly Chinese, historical texts. Joe Cribb has presented a plethora of arguments in a number of publications, finally proposing a date of Kaniṣka around AD 120 or slightly later (Cribb 1990, 1999). The difference between AD 227 and this expected starting date was explained by me on the basis of the well-known theory of the dropped-hundreds, first presented by J. van Lohuizen-de Leeuw (1949, 1986) and taken up by many others, including Plaeschke (1981) and Williams (1989), each adding more arguments. An exact beginning of the so-called Kuṣāṇa-era, starting with Kaniṣka I, would thus be set at AD 127.

Seen against the work of van Lohuizen-de Leeuw and Cribb the formula presented by Sphujiddhvaja some decades after AD 227 was not a big surprise, it only offered the contemporaneous evidence looked for for so long. When this formula was published, the reactions were twofold in nature. The majority of concerned scholars accepted it as a welcome occasion to end the seemingly endless debate on the Kaniṣka date. Serious criticism, however, centred around just one point: Since the last known date of the first Kuṣāṇa century is 98, and the second century is a fact, the dropped-hundred theory might be a misnomer. How can we be sure that the accession of Kaniṣka didn't take place 98 or 103 years earlier than AD 227? That means the difference between Kaniṣka and the definition of the *koṣāṇa* era by Sphujiddhvaja might be exactly 100, but it might also be just close to 100. Let us call this objection the "close-to-100"-theory. It was

brought forward long ago as a possible alternative to the view of van Lohuizen-de-Leeuw e.g. by Rosenfield (1967: 106) and M. Carter (1998: 218 with fn. 14).

It seems to me that the adherents of the "close-to-one-hundred" theory overlook one severe implication of deviating from exactly 100 years dropped: We know from the so-called and much younger *laukika* era that dropped hundreds are not foreign to Indian time-keeping. A continuation of an installed era with dropped hundreds in every century seems therefore to be more plausible than the introduction of a second Kuṣāṇa era with its own, newly defined starting point, slightly earlier or later than 100 years after Kaniṣka. We have no auspicious historical event at hand between AD 225 and, say, AD 230 that could be used to explain the abolishment of the era of Kaniṣka I and the introduction of a new era by Vasudeva or Kaniṣka II.

There is more in favour of van Lohuizen-de Leeuw's theory. The Kuṣāṇa era is the first one in India that definitely restarts counting after the lapse of exactly or roughly 100 years and it is to be expected that this feature of the Kuṣāṇa era was adopted systematically by the adherents of the *laukika* era. Why would the Kuṣāṇas introduce such a method of time keeping? Was it just a comfortable way of dropping unneeded information, as when we say "in 98" and mean, in our days, 1998? If abbreviation was the reason, why then did others wanting to be brief and using different eras, not adapt this method of expression? For example, why do we never¹ get a *śaka* or *vikrama samvat* date of, say, 66, standing for 166 or 466?

The reason may be found in the Kuṣāṇa's habit of looking to the West, to Rome. Their pantheon was Bactrian, Greek and Hellenistic, their title "king of kings" was Iranian, as was their highflying self-designation as *devaputra* (Maricq 1958: 378-382). The weight standard the Kuṣāṇas introduced for their gold coins, was Roman. In their time the Romans fostered the idea of the *saeculum*. Its length was not strictly limited to 100 years, but in the Latin of their time it did, in fact, mean that. If the Kuṣāṇas had the *saeculum* in mind right from the start, then their dropped hundreds are not an abbreviation for brevity's sake but the result of the adoption of yet another Western concept. The idea of a maximal life span and of rejuvenation inherent in the notion of *saeculum* may have led to the idea that after the first round beginning with Kaniṣka I there had to follow a second round with a king bearing just that name. What is for us an embarrassing duplication of dates below 20, referring either to Kaniṣka I or II, may have been seen quite differently by the contemporaries of Kaniṣka II, expecting as they did a duplication of the glorious days connected with that name.

A *saeculum* of 100 years would appear as *varṣasatam* in Sanskrit, /vassasata/, written *vasasata* in many Prakrits. This term is not found in Kuṣāṇa contexts, but it occurs in inscriptions of South India, dating from Kuṣāṇa times, and presenting dates lower than 100. One example from the Sātavāhana inscriptions mentions *sātākamṇisa vasasatāya savacharam 10 2 hemamṭāna pakho 7* (Gai 1962: 241). Others come from the Ikṣvāku dynasty, e.g. *virapurisadatasā vasasatāya*

savacharaṃ vijayaṃ vāsapakhaṃ prathamam (Sircar 1963-64: 3) or *virapurisadatasa vasasatāya samva 10 5 vā[*sapakhe...]* (Vogel 1931-32: 66 M3). The standard formula found in the inscriptions of two dynasties shows that *vasasata* in the dative case did convey a special meaning in addition to the pure registration of the date. An allusion to 100 years seems most probable. Such an ideal of "100 years" could be indigenous, alluding to the life-span, *āyus*, of ideally 100 years. It could as well have been influenced by a foreign concept. In any case, these "100 years", *vasasatāya*, occur at the same times the Kuṣāṇas are designing their system of dynastic reckoning.

So far as counting backwards from AD 227 is concerned, it seems then that the dropped "hundreds" are much more likely than any number dropped "close to one hundred".

2. The Guptas and the "continued era"

After the Kuṣāṇas, the Guptas needed quite some time to adopt the idea of an era from their predecessors. In their first 50 years (ca. AD 320-370) the Śāka era replaces the Kuṣāṇa era at Mathura in rare cases. The Śāka era, used on the coins of the Kṣatrapas of Ujjain, seems to have been continued on the coins of Candragupta II after his taking of Ujjain. Even after Candragupta II had introduced his own dynastic reckoning, another era was kept up concurrently right into the 5th century AD. This concurrent era is of considerable importance, firstly, since it has never been fully understood, and secondly, since it provides a direct argument in favour of the dropped hundreds of the Kuṣāṇas.

When the rule of the Kuṣāṇas had finally faded out, the Guptas arose as the one supreme power in northern India. Their first truly dynastic date is found on the so-called Mathura pillar of Candragupta II. Here, as in three other instances, we encounter the enigmatic term *kālānuvartamānasamvatsare*, "in the year of continuing time", a term which can only be understood by a closer look at all the texts concerned.

2.1. The Mathura pillar inscription

On the Mathura pillar inscription of Candragupta II and at some other places, two dates are found simultaneously. The nature of these two dates was never disputed: any shorter date was regarded as regnal, and any longer date as dynastic. This explanation looks reasonable, but it creates severe problems, as we will see.

The dates on the Mathura pillar are crucial for our purposes. They were first read by Bhandarkar (1931-32: 8) as:

candraguptasya vijarajyasamvatsa[re]..... [gupta]-kālānuvarttamāna-samvatsare ekaśaṣṭhe 60 1[pra]thame śukladivase paṃcamyāṃ, translated as

"In theyear of ...Chandragupta, ...on the fifth of the bright half of the First (Āshādhā) of the

year 61 following the Gupta era."

The letters in the central part of the inscription, represented as ".....[gupta]" in Bhandarkar's edition are abraded beyond recovery. Bhandarkar expected the regnal year to be on the dotted line after *vijarajyasamvatsa* and he introduced his guessed "[gupta]" with confidence (1931-32: 3). Taking 61 to be a dynastic date he saw that it would be the earliest date for Candragupta II so far. In view of the highest date known, 93, he propounded a rule for this king of at least 32 years (1931-32: 4).

This interpretation of "the earliest genuine date of the Gupta era" was maintained by D.C. Sircar (1942: 269 fn. 2), who introduced a new "reading" of the same abraded part. According to him we should read:

*candraguptasya vija<ya>rājya-samvatsa[re] [paṃ]came [5] kālānuvarttamāna-samvatsare
ekaśaṣṭhe 60 1[pra]thame śukladivase paṃcamyāṃ.*

This way we get a regnal year 5 in word and cypher, being equivalent to a dynastic year 61.

Starting the Gupta era in AD 320,² the text should date from AD 381 with Candragupta

Fig. 1: The date of the Mathura pillar from Bhandarkar's rubbing, with the crucial part high-lighted and Sircar's reading from his *Select Inscriptions*.

enthroned five years earlier, i.e. AD 375. This logic has found its way into all the recent history books.

Sircar (1942: 270 fn. 1) read the text from the rubbing as published by Bhandarkar. If we look at this rubbing ourselves (fig. 1) we see that there is no way to find the least trace of either *paṃcame* or 5 and that Sircar's "reading" is mere imagination. We can only say that this text combines an irretrievably lost *viṣṭyārājya-saṃvatsara*-number, whatever that was, with another year counted in "continuing time", whatever that was, and that the sequence of citing was first a) *viṣṭyārājya*, then b) *kālānuvartamāna*.

2.2. The new Yakṣa

Very recently D. Stadtner (2002) published an extraordinary figure of a yakṣa from the time of Kumāragupta. Although some art historians have doubts as to the genuineness of the piece (Bautze-Picron 2002) the inscription offers not the least argument for regarding it as a forgery.³

The date can be read from the plate as:

*kumāraguptasya viṣṭyārājya-saṃvatsare dvādaśotta[ra]-śatatame saṃ (100) [10] 2
kālānuvartamāne paṃcame saṃ 5 varṣāmāse dvitīye 2 divase tritīye 3*, rendered by Stadtner (2002: 26a) as:

"In the victorious ruling year 112 of ... Kumaragupta, in the year 5 of continuous reckoning, in the 2nd month of the rainy season, in the third day".

Here, we see that *viṣṭyārājya* means the dynastic reckoning of the Guptas, as is common in so many other inscriptions of this family. The dynastic reckoning of a year 112 counting from the beginning of the Gupta era leads to a date $320+112 = \text{AD } 432$ ⁴ This year is numbered fifth in the system of *kālānuvartamāna* years. That means that the *kālānuvartamāna* system started in AD 427 with its first year. Stadtner fully realized that "regnal years are not included in Gupta epigraphs", but puzzled by Sircar's "reading" of the Mathura pillar inscription he thought that the short number could "relate to regnal years but in a way that is not yet understood" (26a).

2.3. A Buddhist pedestal

A third piece was published in 1982 by Thaplyal & Sharma, later dealt with by Subramonia Iyer (1973: 20-22, print year 1986) and Sharma (1995: 209). On the pedestal of a standing Buddhist image the donation is dated:

*saṃvatsaraśate ekaviṃśottaraśate 100 20 1 kālā(nu)vartamānasamvatsare pa(m)cadaśe
mārgaśiṣamās(e) divase prathame (1)*.

This was understood by all the editors as follows:

"In the year one hundred and twenty-one - 121 - of current era, in the fifteenth (regnal) year (of the ruling king), in the month of Mārgaśiṣa, on the first day".

On the assumption that two concurrent year dates must necessarily be interpreted as regnal and

dynastic, the editors took the year 121 as referring to the Gupta era and the year *kālānuvartamāna* 15 as regnal. This produced a glaring conflict with the Mathura pillar inscription, where *kālānuvartamāna* is connected with year 61, a number much too high for a regnal year. The editors saw a solution: "The year 15 in this context should therefore be taken as regnal year of the ruling sovereign. The scribe has by mistake referred year 15 as *kālānuvartamāna saṃvatsara*, in fact it is year 121 which should have been referred to as such" (Thaplyal & Sharma 1982: 18).

As will be seen below, it is not necessary to assume a mistake with regard to the terminology. I will show that the scribes knew exactly what the different year types meant.

There remains another, minor, discrepancy. If the unnamed year 121 is a Gupta year, then it should refer to AD 320 + 121 = 441. A concurrent *kālānuvartamāna* year 15 should then have its starting point 15 years earlier, in AD 426. Above, in the case of the Yakṣa, the starting point was AD 427. The difference is slight, but it is there. Several explanations are possible, but it would need more material to make a final choice.⁵

2.4. A lintel

Also relevant for our purposes is one inscription on a lintel published - with references to the earlier editions - by Lüders (1961: 113 § 78). A photograph can be found in Mitterwallner 1983: pl. 10. Without any reference to a king the dedication is dated:

kālānuvarttamānasamvatsare saptate 70 bhādravadadivase saptāviṃśe 20 7,

"In the current seventieth - 70th - year, on the twenty-fourth - 24th - day of Bhādravada (Bhādrapada)." (Lüders)

3. Comparing the data

These four cases can be presented in their chronological sequence and in tabular order:

Text	king	Dynastic year	kāl.-year
Mathura pillar	Candragupta II	(erased)	61
Lintel	(not mentioned)	(not given)	70
Yakṣa	Kumāragupta	112	5
Pedestal	Kumāragupta	121	15

We saw that in Gupta times dynastic years were from some point onwards counted with the label *vijayarājya-samvatsare*. This date precedes in three known cases another one labelled *kālānuvartamāna-samvatsare*. Two relatively late examples from the time of Kumāragupta show that one series of this latter era started in AD 427 or 426. The connected *kālānuvartamāna* years were 5 and

15. The first example from the time of Candragupta II is earlier; its dynastic year is abraded, but its *kālānuvartamāna* year was 61, that means: the earlier year of Candragupta II comes with a higher number than the later one of Kumāragupta! How can this be? The simplest solution is to reckon with dropped hundreds. Seen from Candragupta's year 61 the years 5 and 15 in the time of Kumāragupta should in reality be regarded as 105 and 115. Since Kumāragupta's *kālānuvartamāna* century started in AD 427, the respective century of Candragupta II should have started in AD 327; and his *kālānuvartamāna* year 61 was not AD 320+61 but 327+61, i.e. AD 388 corresponding to a *vijayarājyasamvatsara* around 68. Likewise it becomes apparent that the *kālānuvartamāna* year cannot be used to reconstruct the beginning of a Gupta king's reign. This does not change our view on Gupta chronology in any important way, but it explains the *kālānuvartamāna* system in itself. Since we have to reckon with dropped hundreds, the *kālānuvartamāna* system could have started in any century AD with the decimals 27, i.e. in AD 27, 127, 227, 327 etc. The four examples using the term *kālānuvartamāna* all come from Mathura, not from the east, not from the Gupta capital Pāṭaliputra. Now, which earlier era is likely to be preserved in Mathura, the capital of the former dynasty of the Kuṣāṇas? We know that the Kuṣāṇa era had earlier dropped a number of years, precisely hundred or "close to one hundred". In the former case it started in AD 127, almost perfectly fitting the *kālānuvartamāna* system with its beginning AD years ending in 27.

Therefore, the most likely solution should be: a *kālānuvartamānasamvatsara* is a year that continues (*anuvartamāna*) the previous era (*kāla*) of the Kuṣāṇas. This continuation is attested under this name only in the former capital of the Kuṣāṇas. The system repeats itself after every 100 years and so gives yet more weight to the assumption that the difference of exactly 100 years also separates AD 227, the date given by Sphujiddhvaja, from the real date of Kaniṣka I.

Somewhat surprisingly, the Kuṣāṇa era can be seen to live on for more than a hundred years after the collapse of the founding dynasty.

Acknowledgment

I thank Dr. Ingo Strauch for a continued discussion on all pertinent points and Dr. David Brown for checking the English.

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Footnotes:

¹ There seems indeed to be one exception: The Cālukya grant of Vira Noṇamba (Rice 1879, cf. Kielhorn 1895: 181) is dated *śaka* 366, which for palaeographic reasons must stand for 1366 = AD 1444; in this case not "dropped hundred", but "dropped thousand".

² This date takes into regard the arguments of Bhandarkar (1981: 181-186) and Mirashi (1990), who differ on the nature of the year starting 319, whether it be current or expired. According to Al-Biruni, the Valabhī era starts 241 years later than the Śaka era, which started "current" in 78 AD. So the Vallabhī = Gupta era should likewise start "current" in 319, leading to an "expired" start with 1 in 320 AD.

³ G. Bhattacharya, in a note attached to Bautze-Picron (2003: 70) speaks about "fairly correct Sanskrit"; he objects only to the "ruling year 5" which "cannot be taken as genuine". However, the "year 5" has nothing to do with "ruling".

⁴ It is AD 432 only if Gupta years really started in 319/320 and are counted as expired. Stadtner speaks of AD 431, obviously reckoning with current years. There are uncertainties about the starting year and the method of calculation, which affect the whole argument. However, the uncertainty does not exceed one or two years in absolute calculation.

⁵ A) One of the scribes was simply not well-informed about one of the two eras he combined. Cases of conflicting eras are not unknown. B) The two eras could have a different starting point inside the year. Only if the *kālānuvatamāna* era started between the rains and spring and the dynastic era with spring would *mārgasīrṣa* lead to a number lower by one compared to the second rain month. C) One of the eras might have been counted as current, whereas the other would have been counted as expired.

SILK ROAD ART AND ARCHAEOLOGY

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2004

**Journal of the Institute of Silk Road Studies
The Hirayama Ikuo Silk Road Museum Foundation**